

KNOWLEDGE, PRACTICES, AND CHALLENGES IN LIVING OUT THE FOUR CORE VALUES AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS OF ST. LOUIS SCHOOL OF DON BOSCO, INC.

John David B. Catipay

*Graduate School, St. Paul University Dumaguete, Dumaguete City,
Negros Oriental, Philippines*

ABSTRACT

This study, “Forming Hearts the Bosconian Way,” examined the knowledge, practices, and challenges in living out the four core values—God-Centeredness, Family Spirit, Commitment to Excellence, and Social Responsibility—among Senior High School students of St. Louis School of Don Bosco, Inc. It used a quantitative-descriptive design with a structured survey questionnaire, and data were treated using frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and ranking. Results show that students have a very high level of knowledge of the core values, with Commitment to Excellence obtaining the highest composite mean. In terms of practice, students demonstrate a very great extent of living out the values, especially in Social Responsibility and Family Spirit. However, they still experience minor to moderate challenges, with Commitment to Excellence identified as the most difficult due to lack of motivation, academic workload, and time constraints. Despite these, findings indicate that the school’s formation programs are effective in helping students internalize and apply the core values in their academic, social, and spiritual life. Overall, the study concludes that the Bosconian core values are well understood and practiced, but continued support and reinforcement are needed to sustain and deepen value formation.

Keywords: *Bosconian values, Senior High students, Salesian education*

INTRODUCTION

Education today goes beyond academic achievement and extends to the formation of values, character, and spirituality. At St. Louis School of Don Bosco, Inc., students are

formed to become “good Christians and upright citizens” through the core values of God-Centeredness, Family Spirit, Commitment to Excellence, and Social Responsibility. Guided by the Salesian Preventive System of St. John Bosco, education emphasizes Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness, which foster holistic student development.

Studies show that values education significantly influences students’ moral development, behavior, and engagement in school life (Baring, 2024; Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). Likewise, school climate and structured formation programs contribute to students’ sense of belonging and value internalization (Wang & Degol, 2016; Chen et al., 2025). Catholic education further emphasizes spiritual and moral formation through participation in religious activities, community engagement, and reflective practices (Pope Francis, 2024).

Despite these efforts, students still face challenges in consistently practicing values due to academic pressure, peer influence, and personal and family concerns. This study therefore examines how Senior High School students understand, practice, and experience challenges in living out the four core values, with the goal of improving values formation programs.

Research Questions

1. How do Senior High School Students who graduated from grade 6 and Grade 10 of Don Bosco understand the meaning of each of the following core values:
 - 1.1 God Centeredness;
 - 1.2 Family Spirit;
 - 1.3 Commitment to Excellence; and
 - 1.4 Social Responsibility.
2. How do students live out these values in:
 - 2.1 their classroom life;
 - 2.2 their family life; and
 - 2.3 their relationships with peers.
3. What challenges do students encounter in trying to live out these values daily?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a quantitative-descriptive research design. The respondents were Senior High School students of St. Louis School of Don Bosco, Inc., specifically those who graduated from Grades 6 and 10. A structured survey questionnaire using a Likert scale was employed to measure students’ knowledge, practices, and challenges related to the four core values.

The instrument underwent expert validation and pilot testing, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.940 using Cronbach’s Alpha, indicating high reliability. Data gathering was conducted after securing approvals from the research adviser, school administration, and Ethics Review Committee.

Data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, and weighted mean. The study is limited to Senior High School students of SLSDB, SY 2025–2026.

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Level of Knowledge of the Four Core Values: God-Centeredness

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. I understand the purpose of recollections or retreats in strengthening my faith.	4.42	Very Knowledgeable
2. I understand the meaning of corridor confession during Lent and Advent.	4.48	Very Knowledgeable
3. I understand the importance of attending Masses (Sunday or school-level).	4.59	Very Knowledgeable
4. I understand the significance of First Holy Communion and Confirmation in the Catholic faith.	4.65	Very Knowledgeable
5. I understand the purpose of the feast day procession of St. John Bosco.	4.45	Very Knowledgeable
6. I understand why we pray the Holy Rosary in class or gym.	4.59	Very Knowledgeable
7. I understand the importance of visiting the Blessed Sacrament.	4.45	Very Knowledgeable
8. I understand the purpose of the morning prayer assembly.	4.43	Very Knowledgeable
9. I understand what I learn in Religion class and its relevance to living a God-centered life.	4.46	Very Knowledgeable
10. I understand the message of the Good Morning Talks delivered by the Salesians and the Principal.	4.13	Knowledgeable
Composite	4.47	Very Knowledgeable

Legend:

Likert Scale	Range of Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Very Knowledgeable
4	3.41-4.20	Knowledgeable
3	2.61-3.40	Moderately Knowledgeable
2	1.81-2.60	Slightly Knowledgeable
1	1.00-1.80	Not Knowledgeable

The data in Table 1.1 show that students have a very high level of knowledge of God-Centeredness, as indicated by a composite weighted mean of 4.47. This means that students demonstrate strong understanding of religious practices and their importance in their faith life.

Among the indicators, the highest means were observed in the significance of First Holy Communion and Confirmation, attending Mass, and praying the Holy Rosary. This shows that students are most knowledgeable in structured and regularly practiced Catholic traditions.

Meanwhile, the lowest mean was in understanding the Good Morning Talks, although still interpreted as “Knowledgeable.” This suggests that students understand formal religious practices better than less structured formation activities.

Overall, the findings imply that structured religious practices contribute more to students’ knowledge of faith compared to informal school-based reflections.

Table 1.2
Level of Knowledge of the Four Core Values: Family Spirit

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. I understand how Intramurals build unity and bonding among students.	4.58	Very Knowledgeable
2. I understand the purpose of Educators’ Day in strengthening the school community.	4.43	Very Knowledgeable
3. I understand the role of the Christmas Party in fostering camaraderie and joy.	4.59	Very Knowledgeable
4. I understand how Healthy Dance Competitions or Mass Demonstrations encourage teamwork and bonding.	4.52	Very Knowledgeable
5. I understand the purpose of Family Day in connecting students, teachers, and families.	4.49	Very Knowledgeable
6. I understand the importance of Friendship Day / New Students Day activities in welcoming new students.	4.32	Very Knowledgeable
7. I understand how Youth Night Dance Party helps students interact and build friendships.	4.33	Very Knowledgeable
8. I understand the meaning of recognition events in celebrating achievements together.	4.39	Very Knowledgeable
9. I understand the purpose of Club or Sodality Meetings in developing shared interests and friendships.	4.13	Knowledgeable
10. I understand the purpose of Fun Run in fostering teamwork and school unity.	3.99	Knowledgeable
Composite	4.38	Very Knowledgeable

The data in Table 1.2 indicate that students have a very high level of knowledge of Family Spirit, with a composite weighted mean of 4.38. The highest ratings were observed in understanding the role of the Christmas Party, Intramurals, and group activities in

promoting unity and camaraderie. This shows that students are highly aware of activities that strengthen relationships and school bonding.

However, slightly lower means were recorded in understanding the purpose of Fun Run and Club or Sodality meetings, although still interpreted as “Knowledgeable.” This suggests that students are more familiar with highly participative and celebratory activities than with structured or organization-based programs.

Table 1.3
Level of Knowledge of the Four Core Values: Commitment to Excellence

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. I understand the importance of being punctual for classes and activities.	4.52	Very Knowledgeable
2. I understand the meaning of awarding merits and conduct grades every quarter.	4.64	Very Knowledgeable
3. I understand the significance of graduating or moving up successfully.	4.86	Very Knowledgeable
4. I understand the importance of studying regularly, not just before exams.	4.30	Very Knowledgeable
5. I understand the purpose of maintaining high grades in all subjects.	4.51	Very Knowledgeable
6. I understand why participating in extracurricular activities is important.	4.19	Knowledgeable
7. I understand the value of submitting projects that show effort and creativity.	4.61	Very Knowledgeable
8. I understand why it is important to accept constructive criticism gracefully.	4.62	Very Knowledgeable
9. I understand the meaning of serving responsibly as class officers.	4.43	Very Knowledgeable
10. I understand the purpose of participating in school-organized camps.	4.28	Very Knowledgeable
Composite	4.50	Very Knowledgeable

The data in Table 1.3 show that students have a very high level of knowledge of Commitment to Excellence, with a composite weighted mean of 4.50. The highest ratings were observed in understanding the importance of graduating successfully, earning merits, and accepting constructive criticism. This indicates that students clearly understand the importance of academic success and personal growth.

Meanwhile, slightly lower means were seen in participating in extracurricular activities and school camps, although still within the “Knowledgeable” level. This suggests that while students understand the concept of excellence, some aspects related to participation and engagement may not be as strongly emphasized.

Table 1.4
Level of Knowledge of the Four Core Values: Social Responsibility

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. I understand the importance of zoning or classroom cleaning in keeping the school orderly.	4.16	Very Knowledgeable
2. I understand the purpose of White Gift / Operation 333 in helping those in need.	4.68	Very Knowledgeable
3. I understand the meaning of Lenten Coin in sharing and helping others.	3.91	Knowledgeable
4. I understand the purpose of Mission Fund Drive in supporting communities in need.	4.62	Very Knowledgeable
5. I understand the importance of using eco bags to properly manage waste.	3.90	Knowledgeable
6. I understand why we report or return lost items instead of keeping them.	4.59	Very Knowledgeable

Table 1.4 (continued)

7. I understand the value of honesty during incorrectly checked tests or quizzes.	4.54	Very Knowledgeable
8. I understand why it is important to avoid vandalism.	4.64	Very Knowledgeable
9. I understand the purpose of helping teachers or staff when they need assistance.	4.78	Very Knowledgeable
10. I understand why we greet teachers and staff politely.	4.78	Very Knowledgeable
Composite	4.46	Very Knowledgeable

The data in Table 1.4 indicate that students have a very high level of knowledge of Social Responsibility, with a composite weighted mean of 4.46. The highest ratings were observed in helping teachers, greeting politely, and participating in outreach activities, showing strong awareness of respectful and community-oriented behaviors.

On the other hand, slightly lower means were found in environmental practices such as using eco bags and understanding Lenten Coin, although still interpreted as “Knowledgeable.” This suggests that students are more aware of interpersonal responsibility than environmental responsibility.

Table 2.1
Extent of Practice of the Four Core Values: God-Centeredness

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. I participate in recollections or retreats to strengthen my faith.	4.57	Always
2. I go to corridor confession during Lent and Advent.	4.01	Often
3. I attend Masses regularly (Sunday or school-level).	4.12	Often
4. I value and participate in First Holy Communion and Confirmation activities.	4.43	Always
5. I join the feast day procession of St. John Bosco.	4.57	Always
6. I pray the Holy Rosary in class or during school activities.	4.36	Always
7. I visit the Blessed Sacrament to reflect and pray.	3.86	Often
8. I take part in the morning prayer assembly.	4.67	Always

Table 2.1 (continued)

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
9. I apply lessons from Religion class in my daily life.	4.09	Often
10. I reflect on messages of the Good Morning Talks by the Salesians and the Principal.	3.61	Often
Composite	4.23	Always

The data in Table 2.1 indicate that students practice God-Centeredness to a very great extent, with a composite weighted mean of 4.23, interpreted as “Always.” The highest levels of practice were observed in participating in morning prayer assemblies, recollections or retreats, and feast day processions. This shows that students actively engage in structured religious activities provided by the school.

However, slightly lower means were seen in visiting the Blessed Sacrament, reflecting on Good Morning Talks, and applying Religion lessons in daily life, although still interpreted as “Often.” This suggests that while students consistently participate in organized religious practices, personal reflection and application of faith may be less consistent.

Table 2.2
Extent of Practice of the Four Core Values: Family Spirit

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. I join Intramurals to strengthen relationships with classmates.	4.42	Always
2. I participate in Educators' Day activities to build the school community.	4.38	Always
3. I take part in the Christmas Party to celebrate with peers.	4.68	Always
4. I join Healthy Dance Competitions or Mass Demonstrations for teamwork.	4.45	Always
5. I participate in Family Day activities with families, teachers, and classmates.	4.38	Always
6. I engage in Friendship Day / New Students Day to welcome peers.	4.01	Often
7. I attend Youth Night Dance Party to interact and build friendships.	4.35	Always
8. I celebrate recognition events with classmates to honor achievements.	4.41	Always
9. I attend Club or Sodality meetings to share interests and build friendships.	4.32	Always
10. I take part in the Fun Run to strengthen teamwork and school unity.	3.83	Often
Composite	4.32	Always

The data in Table 2.2 show that students practice Family Spirit to a very great extent, with a composite weighted mean of 4.32, interpreted as “Always.” The highest levels of participation were seen in the Christmas Party, Intramurals, and group-based school activities, indicating strong involvement in activities that promote unity and interaction.

On the other hand, slightly lower participation was observed in Friendship Day and Fun Run activities, though still rated as “Often.” This suggests that while students actively engage in most community-building events, some activities may not be as consistently practiced by all students.

Table 2.3
Extent of Practice of the Four Core Values: Commitment to Excellence

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. I am punctual for classes and school activities.	4.45	Always
2. I strive to earn merits and maintain good conduct each quarter.	4.42	Always

3. I work toward graduating or moving up successfully.	4.72	Always
4. I study regularly, not just before exams.	3.70	Often
5. I aim to maintain high grades in all subjects.	4.26	Always
6. I actively participate in extracurricular activities.	4.10	Often
7. I complete and submit projects that show effort and creativity.	4.45	Always
8. I accept constructive criticism to improve my work.	4.55	Always
9. I fulfill my responsibilities as class officers or group leaders.	4.16	Often
10. I join school-organized camps and activities to improve skills.	4.09	Often
Composite	4.29	Always

The data in Table 2.3 indicate that students practice Commitment to Excellence to a very great extent, with a composite weighted mean of 4.29, interpreted as “Always.” The highest ratings were observed in striving to graduate, accepting constructive criticism, and completing tasks with effort, showing strong commitment to academic goals and personal improvement.

However, lower means were found in studying regularly, balancing extracurricular activities, and fulfilling leadership roles, though still rated as “Often.” This suggests that while students aim for excellence, consistency in effort and time management may still present some difficulty.

Table 2.4
Extent of Practice of the Four Core Values: Social Responsibility

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. I help keep the classroom and school orderly through zoning or cleaning.	4.01	Often
2. I participate in White Gift / Operation 333 to support those in need.	4.62	Always
3. I give Lenten Coin to help others.	3.67	Often
4. I join the Mission Fund Drive to support communities.	4.59	Always
5. I use eco bags and help manage waste properly.	3.78	Often
6. I return lost items instead of keeping them.	4.51	Always
7. I act honestly during tests, quizzes, or school activities.	4.22	Always

8. I avoid vandalism and respect school property.	4.68	Always
9. I assist teachers or staff when they need help.	4.62	Always
10. I greet teachers and staff politely.	4.70	Always
Composite	4.34	Always

The data in Table 2.4 show that students practice Social Responsibility to a very great extent, with a composite weighted mean of 4.34, interpreted as “Always.” The highest levels of practice were seen in greeting teachers politely, respecting school property, and participating in outreach programs, indicating strong awareness and application of respectful and ethical behavior.

Meanwhile, slightly lower ratings were observed in environmental practices such as using eco bags, giving Lenten Coin, and maintaining cleanliness, though still interpreted as “Often.” This suggests that while students demonstrate responsibility in social interactions, environmental practices may need more consistent reinforcement.

Table 3.1
Challenges in Practicing the Core Values: God-Centeredness

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. I actively participate in recollections or retreats due to academic workload.	1.99	Minor Challenge
2. I feel shy or uncomfortable during corridor confession in Lent and Advent.	2.33	Minor Challenge
3. I attend Mass depending on available time.	2.22	Minor Challenge
4. I participate in First Holy Communion and Confirmation activities.	1.74	Not a Challenge
5. I join the feast day procession of St. John Bosco.	1.61	Not a Challenge
6. I pray the Holy Rosary during class or school activities.	1.74	Not a Challenge
7. I visit the Blessed Sacrament when I have available time.	2.20	Minor Challenge
8. I am focus during the morning prayer assembly.	2.26	Minor Challenge
9. I apply the lessons from Religion class to my daily life.	2.03	Minor Challenge
10. I sometimes ignore or forget the messages from Good Morning Talks.	2.68	Moderate Challenge
Composite	2.08	Minor Challenge

The data in Table 3.1 show that students experience a low level of challenge in practicing God-Centeredness, with a composite weighted mean of 2.08, interpreted as “Minor Challenge.” Slight difficulties were observed in participating in confession, attending Mass due to time constraints, focusing during prayer, and applying Religion lessons in daily life.

The highest challenge was forgetting or ignoring Good Morning Talks, which reached a “Moderate Challenge.”

These findings suggest that while students are generally able to practice God-Centeredness, consistency in personal reflection and engagement may still be a concern. Activities that require deeper attention and internalization appear to be more challenging than structured or guided religious practices.

Table 3.2
Challenges in Practicing the Core Values: Family Spirit

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. I join Intramurals even if I feel shy or lack confidence.	1.90	Minor Challenge
2. I participate in Educators’ Day activities.	1.58	Not a Challenge
3. I sometimes do not feel motivated to attend the Christmas Party.	1.77	Not a Challenge
4. I cooperate with classmates during Healthy Dance Competitions or Mass Demonstrations.	1.65	Not a Challenge
5. I join Family Day activities even with family concerns.	1.62	Not a Challenge
6. I feel uncomfortable interacting with new students during Friendship Day activities.	1.87	Minor Challenge
7. I socialize during Youth Night Dance Party.	1.83	Minor Challenge
8. I sometimes feel awkward or uninterested during recognition programs.	1.94	Minor Challenge
9. I lack motivation to attend Club or Sodality meetings.	2.00	Minor Challenge
10. I participate in Fun Run activities.	2.26	Minor Challenge
Composite	1.84	Minor Challenge

The data in Table 3.2 indicate that students experience a low level of challenge in practicing Family Spirit, with a composite weighted mean of 1.84, interpreted as “Minor Challenge.” Slight difficulties were noted in participating in Fun Run, attending club or sodality meetings, and joining activities that require confidence, such as Intramurals and recognition programs.

This suggests that while students are generally comfortable engaging in community activities, some may feel hesitant in situations that require social confidence or active participation. Overall, Family Spirit remains one of the least challenging values for students to practice.

Table 3.3
Challenges in Practicing the Core Values: Commitment to Excellence

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. I arrive on time for classes and school activities.	1.83	Minor Challenge
2. I fell unmotivated to maintain good conduct and earn merits.	1.68	Not a Challenge
3. I sometimes doubt my ability to graduate or move up successfully.	1.68	Not a Challenge
4. I study regularly despite distractions.	2.32	Minor Challenge
5. I feel pressured trying to maintain high grades in all subjects.	2.17	Minor Challenge
6. I balance academics with extracurricular activities.	2.33	Minor Challenge
7. I rush projects instead of showing effort and creativity.	2.04	Minor Challenge
8. I accept constructive criticism gracefully.	1.77	Not a Challenge

Table 3.3 (continued)

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
9. I feel overwhelmed when serving as a class officer or leader.	2.20	Minor Challenge
10. I participate in school-organized camps.	2.00	Minor Challenge
Composite	2.00	Minor Challenge

The data in Table 3.3 show that students experience a low level of challenge in practicing Commitment to Excellence, with a composite weighted mean of 2.00, interpreted as “Minor Challenge.” The highest difficulties were observed in balancing academics with extracurricular activities, studying regularly despite distractions, and handling academic pressure.

These findings suggest that while students are motivated to achieve excellence, managing time, workload, and multiple responsibilities can be challenging. This indicates a need for support in time management and maintaining consistency in effort.

Table 3.4
Challenges in Practicing the Core Values: Social Responsibility

Items/Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. I feel tired or unmotivated to help in classroom or school cleaning.	2.17	Minor Challenge
2. I contribute to White Gift / Operation 333.	1.43	Not a Challenge

3. I sometimes forget or neglect giving Lenten Coin.	1.97	Minor Challenge
4. I participate in Mission Fund Drive activities.	1.57	Not a Challenge
5. I forget to use eco bags or manage waste properly.	2.38	Minor Challenge
6. I feel tempted keep lost items instead of returning them.	1.65	Not a Challenge
7. I am honest during tests or school activities.	1.83	Minor Challenge
8. I sometimes do not mind vandalism when others do it.	2.07	Minor Challenge
9. I hesitate to help teachers or staff because I am busy.	1.62	Not a Challenge
10. I forget to greet teachers and staff politely.	1.57	Not a Challenge
Composite	1.83	Minor Challenge

The data in Table 3.4 indicate that students experience a low level of challenge in practicing Social Responsibility, with a composite weighted mean of 1.83, interpreted as “Minor Challenge.” Slight difficulties were observed in environmental practices such as using eco bags, helping in cleaning, and remembering to give Lenten Coin.

This suggests that while students are generally responsible in their actions, consistency in everyday habits and environmental practices may still need improvement. Overall, students are able to practice Social Responsibility with minimal difficulty.

Table 4
Difficult Core Values to Practice

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Commitment to Excellence	28	40.58
Social Responsibility	16	23.19
God Centeredness	17	24.64
Family Spirit	8	11.59
Total	69	100.00

The data in Table 4 show that Commitment to Excellence is the most difficult core value to practice, as reported by 40.58% of students. This is followed by God-Centeredness and Social Responsibility, while Family Spirit is the least difficult.

These findings suggest that values requiring personal discipline, motivation, and consistent effort are more challenging for students compared to relational values. This implies that students may need more support in sustaining motivation and managing responsibilities.

Table 5
Reasons Why It's Difficult to Practice

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of Motivation	33	47.83
Academic Workload	17	24.64
Lack of Time	7	10.14
Peer Influence	6	8.70
Family Concern	4	5.80
Others:	2	2.90
Total	69	100

The data in Table 5 reveal that the most common reason for difficulty in practicing core values is lack of motivation, reported by 47.83% of students. This is followed by academic workload, while other factors such as lack of time, peer influence, and family concerns were less commonly reported.

This suggests that internal factors, particularly motivation, play a major role in students' ability to practice core values. At the same time, external factors like academic demands also contribute, indicating the need for balanced support systems to help students consistently live out these values.

DISCUSSION

Table 1.1 – God-Centeredness (Knowledge)

The findings indicate that students have a very high level of knowledge of God-Centeredness, which suggests that the school's formation program is effective in strengthening students' understanding of faith-based practices. This means that students are well informed about religious activities such as Mass, sacraments, prayer, and retreats, which are regularly integrated into their school experience. The high scores in structured religious practices imply that consistent exposure to liturgical and devotional activities helps students develop strong religious awareness. However, slightly lower understanding of informal formation activities such as Good Morning Talks suggests that reflective and less structured religious communication is not as deeply internalized. This finding is consistent with Baring (2024), who emphasized that Catholic life formation plays a significant role in fostering moral and spiritual development among students, especially when religious education is systematically integrated into school life. Similarly, Fiandini et al. (2024) highlight that religious education materials and structured formation strategies contribute to strengthening students' spiritual awareness and values formation. Thus, the results suggest that God-centered knowledge is strongly developed through structured religious experiences within the school.

Table 1.2 – Family Spirit (Knowledge)

The findings show that students have a very high level of knowledge of Family Spirit, indicating strong awareness of unity, belonging, and cooperation within the school community. Students are more knowledgeable about highly interactive and celebratory activities such as Christmas Party, Intramurals, and dance competitions, which suggests that they associate Family Spirit with visible and enjoyable social experiences. This implies that experiential activities are effective in helping students understand relational values. However, lower understanding of structured activities such as Club or Sodality meetings suggests that organizational and formation-based dimensions of community building are less emphasized in student awareness. This finding aligns with Domingo et al. (2025), who emphasized that students' engagement in school activities and values programs strengthens their understanding and practice of institutional values. Likewise, Ladaran and Biol (2025) found that school climate significantly influences how students manifest and understand core values. Thus, Family Spirit is well understood, but more structured formation activities may need stronger emphasis.

Table 1.3 – Commitment to Excellence (Knowledge)

The results indicate that students have a very high level of knowledge of Commitment to Excellence, reflecting strong understanding of discipline, academic responsibility, and achievement. Students clearly understand punctuality, academic performance, merit systems, and graduation goals, which suggests that excellence is strongly associated with academic success and behavioral expectations. However, lower understanding of extracurricular participation suggests that students tend to view excellence mainly in academic terms rather than as a holistic value that includes co-curricular development. This finding is supported by Schunk and DiBenedetto (2020), who explain that motivation and learning are strongly influenced by students' understanding of performance expectations. Ryan and Deci (2020) also emphasize that intrinsic motivation is strengthened when learners understand the value of their academic actions. Thus, Commitment to Excellence is strongly understood but still largely academic-centered rather than holistic.

Table 1.4 – Social Responsibility (Knowledge)

The findings reveal that students have a very high level of knowledge of Social Responsibility, indicating strong awareness of ethical behavior, respect, and community service. Students show strong understanding of helping others, respecting authority, and participating in school outreach programs, suggesting that social responsibility is strongly linked to visible moral behavior in school life. However, lower understanding of environmental practices and symbolic values such as eco bags and Lenten Coin suggests that ecological and reflective dimensions are less emphasized. This is consistent with Park and Kim (2023), who emphasize that school climate and engagement significantly influence students' social responsibility. Rosales (2020) also highlights that Catholic social teaching strengthens students' understanding of moral responsibility through lived

practice. Thus, social responsibility is strongly understood, especially in interpersonal behavior, but environmental awareness still needs reinforcement.

Table 2.1 – God-Centeredness (Practice)

The findings show that students practice God-Centeredness to a very great extent, indicating that religious values are actively lived out in school life. Students frequently participate in prayer assemblies, retreats, sacraments, and devotional practices, suggesting that structured religious formation strongly influences behavior. This implies that consistent school-based religious activities help students integrate faith into daily routines. However, lower practice in reflective activities such as applying Religion lessons and responding to Good Morning Talks suggests limited internalization of informal faith messages. This is supported by Macalam et al. (2025), who found that spiritual well-being is strengthened through active participation in religious practices and reflection. Estrada et al. (2019) also emphasize that religious education contributes to moral and spiritual development among adolescents. Thus, students actively practice faith, but deeper reflection remains an area for growth.

Table 2.2 – Family Spirit (Practice)

The findings indicate that students practice Family Spirit to a very great extent, especially through participation in social and school-wide activities. High engagement in events such as Christmas Party, Intramurals, and dance competitions suggests strong involvement in activities that promote unity and belonging. However, lower participation in Friendship Day and Fun Run indicates that confidence and motivation may affect involvement in less familiar or socially demanding activities. This aligns with Chen et al. (2025), who found that school climate and belonging significantly influence student engagement and relationships. Fabris et al. (2023) also emphasize that strong school connectedness promotes positive peer interaction and participation. Thus, Family Spirit is strongly practiced, especially in structured social activities.

Table 2.3 – Commitment to Excellence (Practice)

The findings show that students practice Commitment to Excellence to a very great extent, demonstrating strong academic discipline and responsibility. Students consistently show punctuality, academic effort, acceptance of feedback, and goal-oriented behavior, indicating strong internalization of academic standards. However, lower practice in study habits, extracurricular involvement, and leadership roles suggests challenges in balancing responsibilities. Zimmerman (2002) explains that self-regulated learning is essential for sustained academic success. Gustafsson et al. (2023) also highlight that students often struggle with balancing academic and co-curricular demands. Thus, excellence is strongly practiced but requires better balance and consistency.

Table 2.4 – Social Responsibility (Practice)

The findings reveal that students practice Social Responsibility to a very great extent, particularly in respectful behavior, helping others, and participation in outreach programs. Students consistently demonstrate politeness, honesty, and service-oriented actions, reflecting strong moral behavior. However, lower practice in environmental responsibility suggests inconsistency in ecological habits. Berkowitz and Bier (2005) explain that prosocial behavior is strengthened through reinforcement and consistent practice. Park and Kim (2023) also highlight that school environment plays a major role in shaping responsible behavior. Thus, social responsibility is strongly practiced but environmental consistency needs improvement.

Table 3.1 – God-Centeredness (Challenges)

The findings show that students experience only minor challenges in practicing God-Centeredness, indicating generally stable religious engagement. Difficulties are mainly related to time constraints, attention, and consistency in reflection. Ryan and Deci (2020) explain that motivation and competing demands affect consistency in behavior. Thus, students are generally committed but face minor challenges in sustaining reflection.

Table 3.2 – Family Spirit (Challenges)

The results indicate minor challenges in Family Spirit, particularly in confidence-based and unfamiliar social activities. Fabris et al. (2023) emphasize that school belonging influences participation, while Turan Bora (2025) highlights the role of confidence in engagement. Thus, challenges are minimal and mainly social in nature.

Table 3.3 – Commitment to Excellence (Challenges)

The findings show minor challenges in Commitment to Excellence, especially in balancing workload, study habits, and responsibilities. Schunk and DiBenedetto (2020) explain that academic pressure and self-regulation challenges are common among students. Thus, students are committed but need support in balance and time management.

Table 3.4 – Social Responsibility (Challenges)

The results indicate minor challenges in Social Responsibility, especially in environmental behavior and consistency. Berkowitz and Bier (2005) emphasize that reinforcement is key to sustaining behavior. Thus, students understand social responsibility but need stronger habit formation.

Table 4 – Difficult Core Values

The findings show that Commitment to Excellence is the most difficult value, followed by God-Centeredness and Social Responsibility, while Family Spirit is the least difficult. This suggests that discipline and self-regulation are more challenging than relational values.

Ladaran and Biol (2025) support that values requiring personal discipline are harder to internalize. Thus, academic and spiritual consistency require further support.

Table 5 – Reasons for Difficulty

The results show that lack of motivation is the primary reason for difficulty, followed by academic workload and lack of time. Ryan and Deci (2020) emphasize that intrinsic motivation is essential for sustained behavior. Thus, strengthening motivation is key to improving value practice.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The Senior High School students of St. Louis School of Don Bosco demonstrate a very high level of knowledge of the four core values. This shows that the school has been effective in forming students' awareness and understanding of the values through its religious, academic, and formation programs.

In terms of practice, students are able to translate their knowledge into actual behavior. The four core values are generally practiced to a very great extent, especially in Social Responsibility and Family Spirit. This means that students are not only aware of the values but are also actively living them out in school and social settings.

Among the four core values, Commitment to Excellence stands out as the most practiced but also the most difficult to sustain. Although students strive to perform well academically and fulfill responsibilities, challenges such as motivation, workload, and time management affect consistency.

Overall, the level of difficulty in practicing the core values is low. This indicates that students are generally capable of living out the values, although certain internal and external factors still influence their consistency.

The study also concludes that value formation is influenced by both personal and environmental factors. Internal factors such as motivation and discipline, and external factors such as family support, peer influence, and school environment, all play an important role in shaping students' practice of values.

Finally, the consistent support of teachers, parents, and the school greatly contributes to students' ability to live out the core values. This shows that value formation is a shared responsibility among all stakeholders in the students' development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

For School Administration

The school is encouraged to continue strengthening its values formation programs by integrating the four core values in classroom instruction, religious activities, and school-wide programs. Activities such as Masses, retreats, recollections, outreach programs, leadership formation, and school celebrations should be sustained and enhanced.

Programs that support student growth such as guided reflection activities, mentoring, counseling sessions, and formation days may also be strengthened, especially to address challenges in motivation and academic pressure. The proposed Bosconian Growth Day may be implemented consistently to help students develop balance between academics, discipline, and personal growth.

For Teachers

Teachers are encouraged to continuously integrate core values in teaching strategies and classroom activities. They should provide opportunities for students to practice values through group work, reflections, performance tasks, and real-life applications.

Teachers should also maintain supportive, encouraging, and balanced expectations to help students manage academic workload and sustain motivation in learning and value formation.

For Parents

Parents are encouraged to actively support value formation at home by providing guidance, discipline, encouragement, and emotional support. Their role as primary models of values is important in reinforcing what students learn in school.

Regular communication and cooperation with the school are also recommended to ensure consistency in guiding students' behavior and development.

For Future Researchers

Future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies using a larger and more diverse sample to strengthen generalization of results.

Further studies may also explore other influencing factors such as digital behavior, peer dynamics, family structure, and socio-economic conditions that affect value formation. Qualitative or mixed-method approaches may also be used to gain deeper understanding of students' lived experiences in practicing core values.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher confirms that this study was conducted in accordance with ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from the respondents and relevant

school authorities prior to data gathering. The participants were informed of the purpose of the study and their voluntary participation, including their right to withdraw at any time without any consequence. The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were strictly maintained, and all data collected were used solely for academic and research purposes. The researcher ensured compliance with data privacy and safeguarded the well-being of the students throughout the conduct of the study. There was no conflict of interest in the implementation of the research, and all interpretations of the findings were made fairly and objectively. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and proper acknowledgment was given to all sources of information used in the study. If any form of artificial intelligence was utilized in the preparation of the manuscript, it was done responsibly and transparently for academic support purposes only.

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